

A Study on Perception of Hotel Consumers Towards Goods & Service Tax in Bengaluru

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2020

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Ranganatha, B., and KT Subaschandra. "A Study on Perception of Hotel Consumers Towards Goods & Service Tax in Bengaluru." *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2020, pp. 139–46.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737746>

B. Ranganatha

Research Scholar, Bangalore University

Dr. K.T. Subaschandra

*Associate Professor and Research Guide,
Department of Commerce and Management*

Government RC College of Commerce and Management, Bangalore

Abstarct

GST is an indirect taxstructure introducing with the intention to increases the efficiency of taxation, improves economic growth, and brings the whole nation to one nationalmarket. This helps in removing the cascading effect of tax on tax, and benefit is passed on to the consumers. A simple tax structure can bring about greater compliance, thus increasing the number of tax payers, and inturn helps to increase tax revenues to the government. It subsumed other taxes of indirect taxes, and this will effectively mean that tax amount paid by end-users will reduce. As in Economics, lower the prices more will be the demand for that product, results in more consumption of goods, which will be helpful tocompanies. With this background, the purpose of this study is to explore the perception of consumers of hotels towards GST.

Keywords: Goods and Service Tax, Hotels, Consumer, Price, Consumption

Introduction

Goods and Service Tax (GST) is a comprehensive structure of taxation in India merging most of the indirect taxes into a single system of taxation. GST would be an indirect tax on manufacture, sale, and consumption of goods and services throughout India to replace taxes imposed by the state and central Governments. GST is a consumption-based tax levied on the supply of goods and services whichmeans it would be levied and collected a teach stage of sale or purchase of products based on the input tax credit method. This method allows GST-registered business to claim input tax credit to the value of GST they paid on purchase of products as part of their normal commercial activity. Taxable goods and services are not differentiated from one another and are taxed at a single rate in a supply chain till they reach the consumers. GST is termed as 'One Nation, One Tax, and One Market'.

GST ensures a common threshold limit, irrespective of whether your manufacturer or dealer, either dealing in goods or services. Under the old taxation regime, different indirect taxes have different threshold limit. GST aims at providing a seamless flow of tax-credits

throughout the value chain, and across boundaries of States. This one of the fundamental features of GST. The availability of a seamless flow of input tax credit throughout the supply chain would ensure in removing of cascading of taxes.

Unlike the old indirect tax system, each tax system has a different taxable event like Excise duty on the removal of goods, VAT on sales, etc. supply is the single taxable event to discharge the duty liability. Transaction value method is used in determining the value of taxable supply. It is the actual price paid or payable for the supply of goods or services. Branch transfers will be treated as taxable supply, and requisite levy needs to be charged on such supply. However, such a levy is fully allowed as Input credit. Under the old regime the tax on interstate purchase forms part of the cost of goods. Under GST, the input tax credit is available on interstate inward supply of goods and services.

As India is a federal country, both Centre and States are given the power to levy and collect taxes through appropriate legislation. Both the Centre and State Government have distinct responsibilities to perform according to the division of powers as prescribed in the constitution that needs resources for implementation. Actual GST is therefore, appropriately aligned with the constitutional requirement of fiscal federalism.

When the sale of goods and services takes place within the same state, both taxes are imposed. If the movement of goods occurs between two different states (i.e., an interstate transaction), a combined tax called the IGST or the Integrated GST (SGST + CGST) is collected by the central government. The IGST will replace the previously levied central sales Tax (CST). The tax amount collected as IGST is later distributed to respective state Governments.

Review of Literature

Dr.R. Vasanthagopal (2011) Studied “GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System,” and found that positive impacts are dependent on a neutral and rational design of the GST balancing the conflicting interests of various stakeholders, full political commitment for a fundamental tax reform with a constitutional amendment, the switchover to a flawless GST would be a big leap in the indirect taxation system and also give a new impetus to India’s economic change.

Syed Mohd Ali Naqvi, (2013) Studied “challenges and opportunities of goods and services in India” found that GST would eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution of cost of goods and services where it would eliminate the concept of tax on tax and brings a new concept of tax system of setting off of tax which would, in turn, enhance GDP of the economy and reduce the transaction cost and unnecessary wastage, in turn, reduce the corruption.

According to Shekar (2015), Implementation of GST will emerge as the tax of the future. In the competitive world, income from direct taxes has been reduced, and hence the implementation of GST can increase the country’s revenue through combining all indirect taxes in one single head.

Anshu Ahuja (2017) In the research paper titled “Perception of people towards goods and services tax,” identified that consumers are satisfied, that GST will reduce the tax evasion in the country and will enhance the transparency in the tax structure. He further recommended that the government should give some relaxation to farmers and small-scale businesses to avoid the adverse impact of GST on their income level.

Statement of the Problem

Goods & Service Tax is a very comprehensive tax and one of the significant steps towards the economic development of the country. It is the biggest revolution for the entire country in this decade, and it has a high level impact on the hospitality sector as well. Earlier, the hotel sector used to face a lot of problems such as the cascading effect of tax on tax, lack of uniformity in provisions and tax rates, complexities in administration, etc. GST is the single taxation system in India which

helps in reducing time, cost, and efforts. An implementation of Goods and Service Tax Bill is caught the attention throughout all sectors in India. Hence this study seeks to explore the perception of consumers of the hotels sector towards Goods and Service Tax.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the conceptual framework of Goods & Service Tax.
2. To know and analyze the perception of consumers of hotels towards Goods & Service Tax.

Hypothesis Framed

Ho: There is no significant association between gender and their level of perception towards GST

H^o: There is significant association between gender and their level of perception towards GST

Scope of the Study

The hospitality sector plays a major role in the growth of the country, as its GDP growth is also high. The implementation of Goods and Service Tax has a high impact on different sectors. This study focuses mainly on the perception of consumers of hotels towards Goods and Service Tax, where the scope of the study is limited to the respondents of Bengaluru.

Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature. The primary data has been collected from the different respondents i.e., consumers of Bengaluru. Here the data is collected on the questionnaire basis. The secondary information collected through various websites, books, journals, newspapers etc.

Sample Size

The sample size will be restricted to only 60, which comprised of mainly of people in Bengaluru.

Analysis and Interpretations

Table 1 Showing the Education Qualification of Consumers

Education Qualification	No of respondents	Percentage
Literate	58	97%
Illiterate	02	03%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it is known that 97% of respondents are literate, which means that most of the respondents are aware of GST as goods and services tax followed by 3% are illiterate. It is understood that only few people are unaware of GST and its implementation.

Table 2 Showing the Awareness Level of Respondents about GST

Awareness level	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	58	97%
No	02	03%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, only 3% percentage of the respondents are unaware of GST, where these people have lack of knowledge towards GST, followed by 97% are aware of GST.

Table 3 Showing the Perception of Consumers that Prices will Increase after GST

Consumers Perception	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	10	17%
Agree	23	38%
Neutral	14	23%
Disagree	10	17%
Strongly disagree	03	5%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it is analyzed that 38% of consumers agree prices will increase after GST implementation followed by 23% are in a neutral 17% of consumers agree followed by 5% of respondents strongly disagree on this price fluctuation.

As the majority of consumers' perception was that prices would reach higher than before, because they were unaware of it.

Table 4 Showing the Perception of Consumer Burden

Consumer burden	No of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	10	17%
Agree	18	30%
Neutral	14	23%
Disagree	18	30%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Analysis and Interpretation

As per the above table, about 30% of consumers feel that GST will not burden the consumers in anyway, another 30% of consumers disagree, 23% of consumers are neutral, 17 consumers strongly agree that GST will burden reasons may be increased in price that consumers will have to bear. Most of the consumers feel GST as a burden due to improper knowledge about GST and its implementation.

Table 5 Showing Consumers are Affected by GST in Visiting Hotels

Consumers visiting hotels	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	16	27%
Agree	23	38%
Neutral	13	22%

Disagree	8	13%
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it is analyzed that consumers have changed the perception that prices affect consumers visiting hotels, 38% of consumers agree that GST has affected the consumers in visiting hotels followed by 27% strongly agree that GST has affected them followed by 22% of respondents are neutral and, 13% of the consumers disagree that GST has affected the consumers in visiting hotels.

Table 6 Showing Consumer Visiting Hotels are High Before GST

Pre GST visiting hotels	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	9	15%
Agree	22	37%
Neutral	12	20%
Disagree	15	25%
Strongly disagree	1	2%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The above table interprets that 22% of consumers agree that they used to visit hotels more frequently before GST and 15% of them disagree that visiting hotels were not high before GST and 12% of them choose for neutral and 9% of them strongly agreed that they used to visit hotels more and remaining 1% of them strongly disagree in high visiting hotel.

Table 7 Showing Consumers Visiting Hotels Decreased After GST Implementation

Consumer visiting hotels decreased	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	8	13%
Agree	16	27%
Neutral	15	25%
Disagree	19	32%
Strongly disagree	2	3%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, 32% of consumers disagree that consumer visiting hotels have been decreased after GST implementation, 27% of consumers agree that consumers visiting hotels have been decreased it may be the price fluctuations that happen due change in GST rates, 13% consumers do strongly agree that decrease in consumers in visiting hotels for their meals and 3% of consumer say that consumers visiting hotels not decreased after GST implementation.

Table 8 Showing GST Rates Influencing Consumers in Visiting Hotels

GST rates influencing consumer	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	12%
Agree	21	35%
Neutral	17	28%
Disagree	13	22%
Strongly disagree	2	3%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it can be interpreted that GST rates play a prominent role in consumer behavior since 35% of consumers agree that GST rates influence in visiting hotels and 28% influence on GST rates in visiting hotels and 22% disagree on GST rates in visiting hotels and 12% strongly agree that GST rates influence them in visiting hotels remaining 3% strongly disagree that GST rates will influence in visiting hotels.

Table 9 Showing Frequency of Visiting Hotels before GST

Frequency of visiting hotels	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	12	20%
Agree	14	23%
Neutral	17	28%
Disagree	16	27%
Strongly disagree	1	2%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it is analyzed that 28% of the consumers do frequently visit hotels before implementation of GST and 27% of people disagree that they frequently visit hotels before implementation of GST and 23% consumers agree that they visit hotels and 20% strongly agree in visiting hotels but remaining 2% of consumers strongly disagree in visiting hotels.

Table 10 Showing the Number of Times you Visit Hotels in a Day

Number of time visiting hotels in a day	No of respondents	Percentage
1	38	65%
2	16	27%
3	2	3%
4	1	2%
More	3	5%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above tables, it is interpreted that 63% respondents visit hotels once in a day which means where most of them prefer home rather than hotels and 27% percentage of them visits hotels twice in a day, and 3% of them visit hotels thrice in a day, and 5% of them visit hotels more than four times in a day where this 3% of people usually depend upon hotels for their daily meals.

Table 11 Showing Whether GST is Useful

GST useful	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	27	45%
No	33	55%
Total	60	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table, it is concluded that 55% of respondents feel that the implementation of GST is not useful for the economy, and the remaining 45% of respondents says that it is favor for the economy.

Testing of Hypothesis Using Chi-Square Test

Ho: There is no significant association between gender and their level of perception towards GST

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.625a	4	.047
Likelihood Ratio	5.491	4	.240
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.512	1	.219
N of Valid Cases	60		

Interpretation

The calculated value is 0.047 is less than P value 0.05 since the null hypothesis is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted. It means that there is significant relationship between gender and their level of perception towards GST.

Findings

- GST is a tax rationalized process with an objective of One Nation One Tax. According to this few sectors are satisfied, and some are negatively affected by GST. In the case of hotels as per the research, both consumers and hotels are affected due to the rates that implies on the increase or decrease in prices.
- It has been analyzed that most of the consumers feel that GST is a burden for them, and very few people feel GST is not such a burden for them.
- It shows that more than 50% of consumers are affected by the implementation of GST in visiting hotels. There has been a low in moving on to hotels.
- 38% of consumers agreed upon that prices would increase in prices after GST implementation.
- It is found that 38% of consumers agree that GST rates influence consumers in visiting hotels

- 37% of the consumers disagree that they frequently visit hotels and 27% are in a neutral stage. People do visit hotels only when they are hungry or otherwise they refuse to visit hotels
- It is analyzed that 65% of consumers visit hotels at least once in a day but remaining do not visit much.
- It has been found that 55% of consumers agree that the new tax regime is not useful for the economy, and has changed the consumer's perception towards hotels.

Conclusions

The Indian hotel industry has emerged as one of the key industries driving the growth of the service sector, and thereby the Indian economy. On average about 54% of the total revenue of Indian hotels comes from rooms, followed by food, beverages, and banquet services. GST rates should be minimum on these elements for the growth of the hotels sector because they contribute about 8% share to the GDP of the country. Consumers feel that rates after implementation of GST are high at the same time hotels felt ease to follow a single tax regime without including many taxes in it. The data which is collected from the hotels, as well as consumers, conclude that pre and post-GST has affected the consumers, but there is an effect on the profitability of hotel sectors. Services are included in the GST regime by abolishing many taxes; hotels have AC and Non AC restaurants here the tax rates differ in both cases. In India, there were a majority ruling governments in the center, so they wanted to create the relevant tax reform in our country. Thus they utilized the power and created the history. The government of India is still in the progress of frequently changing the GST slab rates.

References

1. Nitin Kumar (2014), "Goods and Service Tax in India-A Way Forward," "Global Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies," Vol 3, Issue 6, May 2014.
2. Shana and Rohit Bhat. a study on problems of Goods and Services Tax on Hotel Industry in Mysore.
3. Peter S. Spiro. Evidence of a Post GST Increases in the Underground Economy.
4. Deepika Chaplot. Impact of GST on hotel and tourism industry.
5. TAXMANN'S, GST Ready Reckoner 6th edition Guided by; V.S Datey and published by taxmann publications (P) Ltd.
6. Competition Vision, article of - GST implementation and its affected part
7. Websites visited
8. www.wikipedia.com
9. www.investopedia.com
10. www.google scholar.com
11. www.academia.com